

Metal Derivatives of Dialkyl Phosphites. Part II.

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Ti[OP(O)R(OR)]₄, Ti[OP(O)R(OR)]₃Cl, Ti[OP(O)R(OR)]₂Cl₂ and Ti[OP(O)R(OR)]Cl₃ have been prepared by reacting titanium tetrachloride with dialkyl phosphites (ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl) in different molar ratios, and their structure characterised by I.R. spectra. Thermal decomposition, under reduced pressure, of the compounds have also been studied.

We have already reported¹ the synthesis of aluminium derivatives of dialkyl phosphites. The present paper deals with the preparation of titanium derivatives of these compounds. The reactions of titanium tetrachloride with dialkyl phosphites were carried out in different molar ratios using benzene as the solvent. To avoid the side reaction² between dialkyl phosphite and hydrogen chloride liberated during the reactions, the reactions were performed under reduced pressure.

Titanium tetrachloride when heated, with excess of dialkyl phosphite or in the molar ratio 1 : 4, under reflux yielded a product of the composition Ti[OP(O)R(OR)]₄ (I). The reactions may be represented as :

(R = Ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl and *n* = 1(IV), 2(III), 3(II) or 4(I).)

All the above derivatives are insoluble in common organic solvents and they do not melt upto 280°. The properties and analyses of the compounds have been reported in Table 2.

Two structures A and B may be proposed for these compounds.

Infra-red spectra (Table 1) of the compounds along with the free dialkyl phosphites have been taken. The spectra of the free phosphites show a sharp band at 2430 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the P-H stretching vibrations. A sharp band at 1265–1260 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the presence of unbonded phosphoryl group, whereas a sharp band at 1080–970 cm⁻¹ is due to the P–O–C vibrations. From these bands, it is clear that dialkyl phosphites are mainly present as dialkyl phosphonates as has been observed earlier³.

TABLE I

Far Infra-red and infra-red spectra of the compounds

Compounds	$\nu(\text{P-O-C-})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{P-H})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{P-C})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{Ti-O-})\text{P}$
1. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})_2\text{P(O)H}^*$	1080 1050 970	1265	2430		
2. $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O})_2\text{P(O)H}^*$	1080 1030 980	1260	2430		
3. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{P(O)}]\text{TiCl}_3$	1000	1080	2460	722	
4. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{P(O)}]_2\text{TiCl}_2$	1000	1090	2450	720	595-575, 507-495, 415, 400, 375-360, 354.
5. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{P(O)}]_3\text{TiCl}$	1000	1080	2450	720	595-565, 490, 420, 400, 375, 352, 325.
6. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{P(O)}]_4\text{Ti}$	1000	1080	2450	710	557, 402, 350.
7. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7^{\text{n}}\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7^{\text{n}})\text{P(O)}]_2\text{TiCl}_2$	990	1080	2410	700	
8. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7^{\text{n}}\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7^{\text{n}})\text{P(O)}]_3\text{TiCl}$	995	1070	2420	725-690	
9. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7^{\text{n}}\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7^{\text{n}})\text{P(O)}]_4\text{Ti}$	960	1100-1070	2400	740	
10. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{\text{n}}\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{\text{n}})\text{P(O)}]\text{TiCl}_3$	1000	1085	2460	720	
11. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{\text{n}}\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{\text{n}})\text{P(O)}]_2\text{TiCl}_2$	990	1080	2460	720	
12. $[\text{O}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{\text{n}}\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9^{\text{n}})\text{P(O)}]_4\text{Ti}^*$	985-970	1080-1030	2410	720, 695	

* Neat.

Far infra-red spectra of the compounds I, II and III (R = Ethyl) show absorption at 600-325 cm^{-1} characteristic of $\nu(\text{M-O-})\text{P}$ in metal complexes⁴. Infra-red spectra of the compounds I-IV (R = Ethyl, *n*-butyl) show a band at 1100-1070 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to phosphoryl group. The shift to a lower frequency is due to co-ordination of the phosphoryl oxygen to titanium of the other molecule⁵. Another strong absorption band at 1000-960 cm^{-1} is due to P-O-C vibrations⁶. A weak band at 2460-2400 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the partial hydrolysis of the compound during mixing of the sample with nujol for spectral analysis.

Presence of M-O-P bond excludes the possibility of structure B whereas the occurrence of phosphoryl group rules out the structure A. However, rapid rearrangement of the

TABLE 2

Reactants	Amount (g)	Product, state and yield (g)	Analysis					
			%P		%Ti		%Cl	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. TiCl_4 $(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	2.19 10.17	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)]_4$ dark violet solid (6.5)	20.55	20.80	7.90	8.04	-	-
2. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_5\text{H}_7)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	3.44 12.02	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)]_4$ solid, dark violet (11.64)	17.34	17.51	6.90	6.77	-	-
3. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	4.05 16.54	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)]_4$ liquid-brownish yellow (17.05)	14.90	15.11	6.15	5.85	-	-
4. TiCl_4 $(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	9.12 19.80	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)]_3\text{Cl}$ solid dark violet (21.20)	18.66	18.79	10.79	9.69	7.20	7.18
5. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	5.09 13.40	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)]_3\text{Cl}$ solid dark violet (15.50)	15.92	16.06	8.23	8.28	6.30	6.14
6. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	5.68 17.42	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)]_3\text{Cl}$ solid dark violet (18.74)	14.24	14.03	7.44	7.23	5.58	5.36
7. TiCl_4 $(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	11.24 16.32	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)]_2\text{Cl}_2$ solid, yellow (11.35)	16.00	15.78	13.00	12.19	18.00	18.07
8. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	14.93 25.93	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)]_2\text{Cl}_2$ solid, yellow, (31.83)	13.56	13.80	11.34	10.67	15.51	15.82
9. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	3.78 7.71	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)]_2\text{Cl}_2$ solid, yellow (10.00)	12.20	12.27	9.42	9.49	14.35	14.07
10. TiCl_4 $(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	17.65 12.80	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)]\text{Cl}_3$ liquid, brown (24.04)	10.99	10.64	16.25	16.44	35.97	36.51
11. TiCl_4 $(n\text{-OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$	9.56 9.76	$\text{Ti}[\text{OP}(\text{O})(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)]\text{Cl}_3$ solid, dark violet (16.98)	8.87	8.91	13.74	13.79	30.36	30.61

structure B may take place according to the following plausible mechanism ultimately leading to structure C.

The presence of a band at $690\text{--}740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to P-C bond, though this assignment is of doubtful nature⁷. These compounds are likely to be polymers involving -O-P-O- bridges. This is evidently supported by their insolubility in organic solvents.

On the basis of polymeric nature and the spectral data of the above compounds, following structure may be proposed :

X = Cl or dialkylphosphite

Compound II (R = Ethyl, *n*-butyl), when heated under reduced pressure, gave dirty white solid V whose composition was established on the basis of elemental analysis (Table 3). In case of the butyl derivative, the distillate was also collected which was found to be C₄H₉Cl.

Thermal decomposition of the compound III (R = ethyl) and IV (R = *n*-butyl) gave TiCl[OP(O)(OR)R][OPR(O)O] (VI) and TiCl₂[OP(R)(O)O] (VII) respectively (Table 3).

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus with interchangeable glass joints was used. Care was taken to ensure that both reagents and apparatus were moisture free. I.R. spectra were recorded on Beckman Infra-red spectrophotometer D-20 using nujol, unless otherwise mentioned.

Titanium tetrachloride (Riedel) was distilled before use. Dialkyl phosphites (ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl) were prepared^{2,8} and distilled before use. Diethyl phosphite of Koch Light Laboratories Ltd. was also used after distillation under reduced pressure. Benzene and alcohols (ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl) were dried as usual⁹.

Titanium, phosphorus and chlorine were estimated gravimetrically by usual methods.

Reaction between Titaniumtetrachloride and Dialkyl phosphites in excess and in the molar ratio of 1 : 4, 1 : 3, 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 in benzene : Dialkyl phosphite (ethyl, *n*-propyl or *n*-butyl) was added slowly to the flask containing known amount of titanium tetrachloride in dry benzene with constant shaking. Flask was fitted with a water condenser which in turn was connected to suction pump through calcium chloride tube. On the addition of phosphite, flask became considerably hot and HCl gas was evolved. It was allowed to attain the room temperature and the reaction mixture was refluxed in an oil bath at 60°–75° till the reaction subsided (4–5 hrs.). Condenser was removed and the flask was connected to vacuum pump. The compound was dried under reduced pressure (3–4 mm) at 60°–70°.

TABLE 3
Action of heat on Titanium dialkyl phosphonate compounds

Compound taken (g)	Residue (g)	Analysis					
		%P		%Ti		%Cl	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. [(C ₄ H ₉ O)(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ (O)PO] ₃ TiCl (3.5)	[(C ₄ H ₉ O)(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ (O)PO] ₂ Ti[OP(O)(C ₄ H ₉)O] (2.9), V	17.06	16.30	7.92	8.40	—	—
2. [(C ₂ H ₅ O)(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ (O)PO] ₃ TiCl (2.50)	[(C ₂ H ₅ O)(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ (O)PO] ₂ Ti[OP(O)(C ₂ H ₅)O] (1.82), V	21.45	21.61	11.00	11.14	—	—
3. [(C ₂ H ₅ O)(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ (O)PO] ₂ TiCl ₂ (1.68)	[(C ₂ H ₅ O)(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ (O)PO]TiCl[OP(O)(C ₂ H ₅)O] (1.40), VI	18.50	18.87	14.90	14.58	10.75	10.81
4. [(C ₄ H ₉ O)(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ (O)PO]TiCl ₃ (2.23)	[O(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ (O)PO]TiCl ₂ (1.61), VII	12.00	12.16	18.90	18.79	27.70	27.83

The yellow coloured compounds obtained from 1 : 4 and 1 : 3 ratios attained green colour after keeping overnight and finally became dark violet, while in case of others no colour change occurred. The results have been given in Table 2 (1-11).

A known amount of compound I (R = ethyl) was heated under reduced pressure (100°/1 mm) for 1½ hr and residue obtained was analysed : Ti, 11.25 and P. 21.50%.

Compounds II (R = ethyl, *n*-butyl), III (R = ethyl) and IV (R = *n*-butyl) were heated under reduced pressure (100°-120°/1 mm) and residues obtained were analysed (Table 3, 1-4).

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REFERENCES

1. D. M. Puri and Attam Parkash, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1972, **49**, 77.
2. J. C. Bailar, *Inorganic Syntheses*, Edn., 1953, V, 58.
3. G. O. Doak and Leon D. Freedman, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 31.
4. C. M. Mikulski, N. M. Karannis, M. J. Strocko, L. L. Pytlewski and M. M. Labes, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 2053.
5. G. H. Dahl and B. P. Block, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **6**, 1439.
6. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", J. Wiley & Sons, New York, Edn. (1958), p. 315.
7. L. J. Bellamy, *ibid.*, p. 321.
8. Ya. A. Mandel Baum, A. L. Itskova and N. N. Melnikov, *Khim. Org. Soedin, Fosfora, Akad. Nauk. S.S.S.R., Otdel. Obshch. Tekh Khim.*, 1967, 288; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **69**, 43338h.
9. D. M. Puri and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1961, **3**, 247; 1962, **4**, 393.